

Hypertrophic Osteoarthropathy a Rare Extra-intestinal Manifestation in a Case of Non-Specific Colitis: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Hypertrophic osteoarthropathy (HOA) is an uncommon syndrome characterized by digital clubbing, periostitis of long bones, and arthralgia or joint swelling. While it is most frequently associated with pulmonary diseases particularly bronchogenic carcinoma¹, cystic fibrosis¹, and chronic lung infections it can also occur in non-pulmonary systemic conditions. Gastrointestinal associations are rare, with most cases reported in longstanding inflammatory bowel disease² (IBD), such as Crohn's disease or ulcerative colitis⁵. The occurrence of HOA in the context of non-specific colitis, particularly as an early or presenting feature, is exceedingly rare.

Case Summary: We report a case of 31-year-old man, presented with progressive joints pain and digital clubbing, without cardio-respiratory symptoms. Imaging confirmed periosteosis suggestive of hypertrophic osteoarthropathy. Comprehensive pulmonary and oncologic evaluations were unremarkable. Gastrointestinal workup, initiated in response to mild but persistent abdominal discomfort and altered bowel habits, revealed patchy colonic mucosal inflammation. Histopathology confirmed the diagnosis of non-specific colitis, without features of Crohn's disease or ulcerative colitis. The patient responded to NSAIDs and mesalazine, with partial resolution of musculoskeletal symptoms.

Conclusion: This case highlights the potential for non-specific colitis to manifest with systemic complications such as HOA, even before classic gastrointestinal features become apparent. Clinicians should maintain a high index of suspicion for atypical presentations of HOA and consider gastrointestinal sources when common cardio-pulmonary causes are excluded. Early diagnosis can lead to appropriate management and prevent unnecessary delays in treatment.

Keywords: Hypertrophic osteoarthropathy, Periosteosis, Colitis, Clubbing, Extra-intestinal

INTRODUCTION:

Hypertrophic osteoarthropathy (HOA) is a rare syndrome defined by the triad of digital clubbing, periosteosis of tubular bones, and joint symptoms, such as arthralgia and swelling. It can be classified into primary (pachydermoperiostosis) and secondary forms, the latter accounting for the majority of cases. Secondary HOA is most often associated with pulmonary pathology, including bronchogenic carcinoma, mesothelioma, chronic lung infections, and cystic fibrosis^{1,8}. The pathogenesis is not fully understood but is believed to involve vascular endothelial growth factor³

(VEGF) and other circulating mediators⁴ that induce periosteal bone formation and increased vascular permeability. Although rare, non-pulmonary causes of secondary HOA have been documented, particularly in association with cyanotic heart disease, liver cirrhosis, and inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). In IBD, HOA has been observed as a rare⁵ extra-intestinal manifestation, more commonly in ulcerative colitis than in Crohn's disease. The occurrence of HOA in association with non-specific colitis, however, is extremely uncommon and remains poorly described in the literature. Non-specific colitis is a histopathological

diagnosis characterized by chronic inflammation in the absence of classic features of ulcerative colitis or Crohn's disease, often representing an early or indeterminate stage of inflammatory bowel pathology. Here, we present a case of secondary HOA as the initial clinical manifestation⁸ in a patient who was subsequently diagnosed with non-specific colitis¹. To our knowledge, this is one of the few documented cases in which HOA preceded the diagnosis of colitis, underscoring the importance of considering gastrointestinal origins in

patients presenting with unexplained HOA and no evident thoracic pathology.

CASE SUMMARY:

A 31-year-old male presented to the outpatient clinic with a 2-year history of bilateral wrist and ankle pain, morning stiffness, and recent swelling in the fingers and toes (fig-1&2). He also reported mild abdominal bloating, intermittent non bloody diarrhea, and weight loss (5 kg over two months), without fever, cough, or cardio-respiratory symptoms.

(Fig -1)

(Fig-2)

Past medical history was found to be non significant and family history was negative for any autoimmune or gastrointestinal disorders. Patient was non smoker, non alcoholic and had no drug history. On physical examination vitals were normal. Musculoskeletal examination reveals digital clubbing of fingers and toes which was associated with tenderness over distal forearms and legs, joint swelling was non synovitic.

On Laboratory investigations ESR - 62mm/hr. CRP -24mg/l. CBC, Liver and Renal panel and thyroid profile were normal. Autoimmune panel i.e Rheumatoid factor, anti-CCP, ANA, HLA B-27 were negative.

Radiographs:

X-rays of the forearms and lower legs showed periosteal new bone formation along the radius, ulna, tibia, and fibula—characteristic of hypertrophic osteoarthropathy. (Fig-3 & 4)

(Fig-3).

(Fig-4)

Chest imaging:

Chest X-ray: revealed no parenchymal disease, effusion, or mediastinal mass.

CECT Abdomen and Thorax: No significant abnormality detected

2D - Echocardiography: LVEF - 55%, Normal all four cardiac chambers, mild MR, mild TR, TAPSE -Normal, Normal LV systolic function, No LV Clot / PE/ Vegetation

GI evaluation:

Upper GI Endoscopy: Multiple duodenal erosions seen (fig-5)

Colonoscopy: Ulceration seen in transverse colon and caecum (fig-6)

(Fig- 5)

(Fig-6)

Duodenal, Transverse colon and caecum biopsy:

Deep cuts and serial sections examined show multiple bits of mucosa showing presence of mucosal glands. The lamina propria shows dense and diffuse chronic inflammatory infiltrate including fair number of eosinophils. No evidence of cryptitis, crypt abscess or crypt distortion seen in sections examined.

Findings:

Findings are suggestive of Non-specific colitis.

Diagnosis:

- **Primary Diagnosis:** Secondary hypertrophic osteoarthropathy.
- **Underlying Cause:** Newly diagnosed non-specific colitis.

Treatment:

Started with NSAIDs (naproxen 500 mg BID) for symptom relief and Mesalazine 2.4 g/day for colitis. On follow up patient got symptomatic relief.

DISCUSSION:

HOA is most commonly associated with cardio pulmonary disorders⁷ particularly lung carcinoma and chronic infections. When no thoracic cause is found, other systemic diseases must be considered. Gastrointestinal causes of HOA are extremely rare and mostly associated with established inflammatory bowel diseases⁶.

Our case is distinctive in that, HOA symptoms were the initial presenting complaint and Colitis was newly diagnosed after HOA had manifested. There was no evidence of malignancy or cardio thoracic disease. The underlying mechanism of HOA may involve increased circulating growth factors (e.g., VEGF, platelet-derived growth factor^{10,11}), which stimulate periosteal bone formation. Chronic intestinal inflammation may trigger these pathways even before classic GI symptoms become prominent hence prompt recognition of HOA and its underlying cause is vital to avoid unnecessary investigations and delay in appropriate treatment.

CONCLUSION:

This case illustrates a rare but important association of hypertrophic osteoarthropathy with non-specific colitis⁹. Clinicians should be aware that HOA can serve as an early or presenting manifestation of gastrointestinal pathology, even in the absence of significant GI

symptoms. Recognition of this link can expedite diagnosis and targeted management.

HOA, though most often cardio-pulmonary in origin, may be a rare manifestation of gastrointestinal disease and Non-specific colitis can present with systemic signs like digital clubbing and periosteosis even before full-blown intestinal symptoms. Thorough evaluation including GI workup should be considered when typical causes of HOA are excluded.

Patient Consent:

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for the publication of this case report.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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